

Selected works for SLR

#	Authors	Title	Year	RQ
1	Ahmed et al.	Evaluating the Demand for Soft Skills in Software Development	2012	RQ1
2	Alves and Rocha	Qualifying Software Engineers Undergraduates in DevOps - Challenges of Introducing Technical and Non-technical Concepts in a Project-oriented Course	2021	RQ2
3	Andersson and Logofatu	Using cultural heterogeneity to improve soft skills in Engineering and computer science education	2018	RQ2
4	Angeli et al.	A Constructivist Redesign of a Graduate-level CS Course to Address Content Obsolescence and Student Motivation	2020	RQ2
5	Barros and Bittencourt	Evaluating the Influence of PBL on the Development of Soft Skills in a Computer Engineering Undergraduate Program	2018	RQ2
6	Bastarrica et al.	What can students get from a software engineering capstone course?	2017	RQ2
7	Brito et al.	Moving to Project-Based Learning at the Program Level: An Experience Report	2020	RQ2
8	Byrne et al.	Development of a Scale for Measuring Students' Attitudes Towards Learning Professional (i.e., Soft) Skills	2020	RQ1, RQ2
9	Caeiro-Rodríguez et al.	Teaching Soft Skills in Engineering Education: A European Perspective	2020	RQ1, RQ2
10	Carroll et al.	E-portfolios for developing transferable skills in a freshman engineering course	2007	RQ1
11	Carter	Ideas for Adding Soft Skills Education to Service Learning and Capstone Courses for Computer Science Students	2011	RQ1, RQ2
12	Cukierman and Palmieri	Soft Skills in Engineering Education - A practical experience in an undergraduate course	2014	RQ1, RQ2
13	Davis and Rebelsky	Developing Soft and Technical Skills Through Multi-Semester, Remotely Mentored, Community-Service Projects	2019	RQ2
14	Deep et al.	Improving the soft skills of engineering undergraduates in Malaysia through problem-based approaches and e-learning applications	2019	RQ2
15	Fioravanti et al.	Assessing the Development of Soft Skills for Project Management using PBL: A Case Study	2020	RQ2
16	Freitas et al.	Mind the gap: bridging the transversal and transferable skills chasm in a public engineering school.	2018	RQ1
17	Galster et al.	Toward Enhancing the Training of Software Engineering Students and Professionals Using Active Video Watching	2018	RQ2
18	Garcia et al.	The effects of game-based learning in the acquisition of "soft skills" on undergraduate software engineering courses: A systematic literature review	2020	RQ2
19	Garousi et al.	Aligning software engineering education with industrial needs: A meta-analysis	2019	RQ1, RQ2
20	Giacaman and Sinnen	Preparing the software engineer for a modern multi-core world	2018	RQ2
21	González-Morales et al.	Teaching "soft" skills in Software Engineering	2011	RQ1, RQ2
22	Groeneveld et al.	Exploring the Role of Creativity in Software Engineering	2021	RQ1

23	Hazzan	Exponential Competence of Computer Science and Software Engineering Undergraduate Students	2021	RQ1
24	Huffman et al.	Use of Marketing and Gamification to Promote Participation in Extracurricular Experiences Focused on Transferable Skill Development	2019	RQ2
25	Ibrahim and Abd Halim	Generic Framework Design of Project-Oriented Problem-Based Learning (POPBL) for Software Engineering Courses	2014	RQ2
26	Khakurel and Porras	The Effect of Real-World Capstone Projects in an Acquisition of Soft Skills Among Software Engineering Students	2020	RQ1, RQ2
27	Konings and Legg	Delivering an Effective Balance of Soft and Technical Skills within Project-Based Engineering Courses	2020	RQ1, RQ2
28	Kulkarni et al.	Adoption of the Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate approach to the Third Year Project in a team-based design-build environment	2020	RQ2
29	Kuppuswamy and Mhakure	Project-based learning in an engineering-design course – developing mechanical- engineering graduates for the world of work	2020	RQ2
30	Lyz et al.	Blended Learning and Self-Reflection as Tools for Developing IT-Students' Soft Skills	2020	RQ2
31	Magano et al.	Project management in engineering education: Providing generation Z with transferable skills.	2021	RQ2
32	Matturro	Soft Skills in Software Engineering - A Study of Its Demand by Software Companies in Uruguay	2013	RQ1
33	Matturro et al.	A Systematic Mapping Study on Soft Skills in Software Engineering	2019	RQ1
34	Matturro et al.	Soft Skills in Software Development Teams - A Survey of the Points of View of Team Leaders and Team Members	2015	RQ1
35	Maxim et al.	Use of Role-play and Gamification in a Software Project Course	2017	RQ2
36	Maxim et al.	Student Engagement in Active Learning Software Engineering Courses	2019	RQ2
37	Milczarski et al.	Soft Skills Development in Computer Science Students via Multinational and Multidisciplinary GameDev Project	2021	RQ2
38	Nicola et al.	The role of education in the acquisition of 21st-century soft skills by Engineering students	2018	RQ2
39	Panthalookaran	Gamification of Physics Themes to Nurture Engineering Professional and Life Skills	2018	RQ2
40	Pawar et al.	Evolving Product Development Skills Through Group-Based Activity Instructions in Engineering Exploration Course	2020	RQ2
41	Pérez and Rubio	A Project-Based Learning Approach for Enhancing Learning Skills and Motivation in Software Engineering	2020	RQ2
42	Pinto and Silva	Gamification applied for Software Engineering teaching-learning process	2017	RQ2
43	Ramos et al.	TBL as an active learning-teaching methodology for software engineering courses	2018	RQ2
44	Rhodes et al.	Concurrent direct assessment of foundation skills for general education.	2018	RQ2
45	Ribeiro and Bittencourt	A PBL-Based, Integrated Learning Experience of Object-Oriented Programming, Data Structures, and Software Design	2018	RQ2
46	Schipper and Van Der Stappen	Motivation and attitude of computer engineering students toward soft skills	2018	RQ1

47	Sedelmaier and Landes	Software Engineering Body of Skills (SWEBOS)	2014	RQ1
48	Souza et al.	A systematic mapping study on game-related methods for software engineering education	2018	RQ2
49	Stray et al.	Exploring human factors of the Agile software tester	2021	RQ1
50	Taylor	Investigating Soft Skills Development at a Higher Education Institution in South Africa	2019	RQ1
51	Valero et al.	Embedding employability and transferable skills in the curriculum: a practical, multidisciplinary approach.	2020	RQ1, RQ2
52	Van Laar et al.	The relation between 21st-century skills and digital skills: A systematic literature review	2017	RQ1
53	Younis et al.	Developing Parallel Programming and Soft Skills: A Project-Based Learning Approach	2021	RQ2
54	Younis et al.	Case Study: Using Project-Based Learning to Develop Parallel Programming and Soft Skills	2019	RQ2
55	Zheng et al.	Practicing and Evaluating Soft Skills in IT Capstone Projects	2015	RQ1, RQ2
56	Zmeev and Zmeev	Project-Oriented Course of Software Engineering Based on Essence	2020	RQ2